

Synthesis and characterization of oxovanadium(IV), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and palladium(II) complexes of some coumarin-based Schiff bases

B. Rupini^a, K. Mamatha^b, R. Mogili^b, M. Ravinder^b and S. Srihari^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Sri Venkateswara Degree College, South Campus, Delhi University, Delhi-110 007, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : sriharisomu@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 14 June 2006, revised 7 May 2007, accepted 11 May 2007

Abstract : The complexes of VO²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Pd²⁺ complexes of Schiff bases derived from the condensation reaction of 3-(2-amino-4-thiazolyl)coumarin with 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde have been prepared and characterized. All the three ligands function as uninegative, bidentate coordinating ligands with metal ions through phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen. The geometry and the bonding characteristics of the complexes have been arrived at from the electronic and ESR spectral data.

Keywords : Schiff base, coumarin derivatives, transition metal ions.

Coumarin, 2H-1-benzopyran-2-one, is a natural product found widely in the plant kingdom. Coumarin derivatives with hydroxy, acetyl, amino, etc. substituents have proved to be potential chelating agents. Metal complexes of various coumarin derivatives have been synthesized and characterized over the years¹. Coumarins attract an immense interest because of their diverse pharmacological applications². Owing to the importance associated with this class of compounds, we present, herein the synthesis and characterization of VO²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Pd²⁺ complexes of coumarin-based Schiff bases namely 3-[2-(2-hydroxybenzylideneamino)-4-thiazolyl]coumarin (HBA TC), 3-[2-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylideneamino)-4-thiazolyl]coumarin (HMATC) and 3-[2-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyleneamino)-4-thiazolyl]coumarin (HNATC) (Fig. 1).

Ar = 2-OH-C₆H₄, 2-OH-3-OMeC₆H₃, 2-OH-C₁₀H₆

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

All the metal complexes are stable at room tempera-

ture and are non-hygroscopic. They are insoluble in water, slightly soluble in methanol and fairly soluble in DMF and DMSO. All the metal complexes which are non-electrolytic in DMF give satisfactory C, H, N and M analyses corresponding to 1 : 2 metal-organic ligand stoichiometry. The magnetic studies reveal that VO²⁺, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of all the three ligands are paramagnetic to the extent of one, three, two and one unpaired electrons respectively and that Pd^{II} complexes are diamagnetic.

The ligands HBATC, HMATC and HNATC show somewhat a broad, small or medium intensity band around 3400 cm⁻¹ that has been assigned to νO-H. This band disappears in the spectra of their complexes indicating that the deprotonation of the group has taken place. A small or medium intensity band around 1250 cm⁻¹ in the ligands assignable to νC-O has undergone a positive shift by 12-32 cm⁻¹ in the complexes suggesting coordination through phenolic oxygen³. The ligands display a strong absorption band around 1720 cm⁻¹ due to νC=O of lactone and this remains unshifted in the spectra of the complexes indicating non-participation of oxygen of this group in coordination. A strong band that shows up in the ligands at 1605 cm⁻¹ due to νC=N has been found lower shifted by about 10 cm⁻¹ in the complexes suggesting the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in coordination⁴. Further, the presence of a broad trough around 3400 cm⁻¹ in

the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes points to the presence of coordinated water in them which is further confirmed by the appearance of a non-ligand band at 833 cm^{-1} assignable to rocking mode of coordinated water⁵. A sharp band which appears at 970 cm^{-1} in the VO^{2+} complexes has been assigned to $\nu\text{V}=\text{O}$ ⁶. The coordination through phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen of the ligands is further evidenced by the appearance, in all the complexes, of non-ligand bands in the far infrared region around 540 and 420 cm^{-1} assignable respectively to $\nu\text{M}-\text{O}$ and $\nu\text{M}=\text{N}$ vibrations⁷. Thus, the ligands function as mononegative, bidentate ones coordinating with the metal ions through phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms.

The present VO^{2+} complexes each show, in their electronic spectra, three peaks around 14500 , 16600 and 25500 cm^{-1} which may be assigned respectively to the transitions ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E_2$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ of square-pyramidal geometry⁸. The Co^{II} complexes each show three peaks around 9300 (ν_1), 16700 (ν_2) and 22200 (ν_3) cm^{-1} assignable respectively to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and similarly Ni^{II} complexes three peaks around 9500 (ν_1), 14200 (ν_2) and 24400 (ν_3) cm^{-1} due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ of octahedral geometry⁹. The Racah interelectron repulsion parameter (B), ligand field splitting energy ($10Dq$) and nephelauxetic parameter (β) for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes have been evaluated⁹ (Table 1). Based on the values obtained, the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes may be arranged with respect to orbital overlap and extent of covalency as

(where $\text{M} = \text{Co}, \text{Ni}$)

The Cu^{II} complexes show each two peaks around 16400 and 20000 cm^{-1} that could be assigned respectively to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$. Based on these observations and the analytical data, the complexes have been

Table 1. Electronic spectral data of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes

Metal complex	Frequency (cm^{-1})			B (cm^{-1})	$10Dq$ (cm^{-1})	β
	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3			
$\text{Co}(\text{HBATC-H})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	9350	16750	22220	728	7400	0.750
$\text{Co}(\text{HMATC-H})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	9320	16630	22800	765	7312	0.788
$\text{Co}(\text{HNATC-H})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	9370	16800	22180	725	7426	0.747
$\text{Ni}(\text{HBATC-H})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	9520	14290	24390	675	9520	0.655
$\text{Ni}(\text{HMATC-H})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	9380	14120	24500	698	9380	0.678
$\text{Ni}(\text{HNATC-H})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	9530	14200	24300	661	9530	0.642

assigned a square planar structure⁹. The Pd^{II} complexes show each three peaks around 14000 , 16600 and 25000 cm^{-1} that could be assigned, in the increasing order of frequency, to the transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ of square-planar geometry⁹.

The schematic drawing of metal complexes formed with the representative ligand HBATC is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2

The ESR spectra of representative VO^{2+} and Cu^{II} complexes are reproduced and the parameters calculated for all the complexes using appropriate equations¹⁰ are presented in Table 2. The ESR spectra of VO^{2+} complexes are appropriately resolved with parallel and perpendicular components corresponding to hyperfine coupling with vanadium nucleus of $I = 7/2$. The spectra of Cu^{II} complexes are of anisotropic nature in that each of them has two peak envelopes, one of small intensity towards low field and the other of large intensity towards high field. The small intensity envelope towards low field has been resolved into two to four peaks due to hyperfine interaction with copper nucleus ($I = 3/2$) while the large intensity peak towards high field remains unresolved. The parameters calculated for the complexes using appropriate equations¹⁰ are presented in Table 2. The g and A values observed for the VO^{2+} complexes are in agreement with those generally observed for a vanadyl complex with a square-pyramidal geometry¹¹. For all the complexes, $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp} < g_e$ (where g_e is free electron value equal to 2.0023) which indicates that the unpaired electron is in the d_{xy} orbital with 2B as the ground state¹².

In the Cu^{II} complexes, it is found that $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2$ indicating that the unpaired electron lies in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital with ${}^2B_{1g}$ as the ground state. The α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 values

Table 2. ESR data of VO²⁺ and Cu^{II} complexes

Metal complex	$g_{ }$	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	$A_{ } \times 10^4$ (cm ⁻¹)	α^2	β^2	γ^2
VO(HBAC-H) ₂	1.94	1.99	1.97	150	-	-	-
VO(HMATC-H) ₂	1.94	2.00	1.98	140	-	-	-
VO(HNATC-H) ₂	1.95	1.99	1.98	138	-	-	-
Cu(HBAC-H) ₂	2.25	2.05	2.12	60	0.66	0.93	0.87
Cu(HMATC-H) ₂	2.25	2.05	2.12	63	0.68	0.90	0.85
Cu(HNATC-H) ₂	2.23	2.04	2.10	67	0.66	0.86	0.67

for the complexes are in the ranges 0.66–0.68, 0.86–0.93 and 0.67–0.87 suggesting appreciable/moderate/weak in-plane σ -bonding, in-plane π -bonding and out-of-plane π -bonding respectively¹⁰.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. or B.D.H. grade. 3-(2-Amino-4-thiazolyl)coumarin¹³ and the ligands HBAC, HMATC and HNATC¹⁴ were prepared as reported earlier. VO²⁺ complexes of the ligands were prepared taking vanadyl sulphate, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes taking respective metal acetates and Pd^{II} complexes using palladium chloride. In the preparation of the metal complexes, the metal and the ligand were combined in 1 : 2 mole ratio using required quantities of methanol or water for the metal salts and methanol or methanol-DMF (20 : 1) for the ligands so as to effect their solubility. The contents were refluxed on a water bath for 2–3 h, the solid that separated was filtered, washed with water, hot methanol and ether and dried in air.

The elemental analyses of the complexes were carried out employing Elemental analyzer, model Carlo Erba 1108. Conductance measurements were made in DMF at 10⁻³ M concentration on a Digisun digital conductivity meter, DI 909 model. Magnetic measurements on complexes were made at room temperature using CAHN instrument model 7550-03 and diamagnetic corrections were calculated from Pascal's constants¹⁵. The IR spectra of the ligands and the metal complexes in KBr were recorded in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ using JASCO FT/IR 5300 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra of the metal complexes were recorded on Shimadzu UV-VIS spectrophotometer UV-160A and JASCO 7800 UV-VIS spectrophotometer. The Varian E-4 X-band spectrophotometer operating in the frequency range 8.8–9.6 GHz was employed in recording ESR spectra of the VO²⁺ and

Cu^{II} complexes in DMF at LNT. The metal content in the complexes, after decomposition with conc. HNO₃, was determined by standard procedures – V by colorimetry, Co by complexometry, Ni and Pd by gravimetry and Cu by iodometry¹⁶.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Head, Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal for providing the necessary facilities.

References

1. P. P. Hankare, S. R. Navarane, V. M. Bhuse, S. D. Dalekar and A. H. Jagtap, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 1464; K. B. Gudasi, T. R. Goudar and M. V. Kulkarni, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 1459.
2. J. Casley, J. Smith and I. Coll, *Phys. Surg.*, 1993, **22**, 67; D. A. Egan, R. O. Kennedy, E. Moran, D. Cox, E. Posser and R. D. Thornes, *Drug Metab. Rev.*, 1990, **22**, 503.
3. J. Joseph and B. H. Mehta, *Russ. J. Coord. Chem.*, 2007, **33**, 124.
4. A. Syamal, D. Kumar and Ahmed, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 634.
5. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970.
6. A. Rana, R. Dinda, P. Sengupta, L. R. Falvello and S. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 2002, **21**, 1023.
7. A. Syamal and M. R. Maurya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 836.
8. S. Purohit, A. P. Koley, L. S. Prasad, P. T. Manoharan and S. Ghosh, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **28**, 3735.
9. K. Mamatha, B. Rupini and S. Srihari, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 950.
10. S. G. Kulkarni, D. V. Jahagirdar and D. D. Khanolkar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 251.
11. C. J. Carrano, C. M. Nunn, R. Quan, J. A. Bonadies and V. L. Pecoraro, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 941.
12. B. P. Yadava, B. P. Shukla and B. Singh, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1990, **60A**, 33.
13. C. F. Koelsch, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2993.
14. U. Veerabhadraiah, Ph.D. Thesis, Kakatiya University, Warangal, India, 1989.
15. J. Lewis and R. G. Wilkins, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1967, 403.
16. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman, 3rd ed., 1961, pp. 791, 358, 479, 512, 443.